

APPROACHES AND METHODS IN DISTANCE LEARNING OF THE ENGLISH LANGUAGE

Umarova Feruza Nigmatovna

*Senior teacher of English department
“TIAME” National Research University*

Abstract. The method of distance education today has almost the same level as traditional education. This method is widely used especially in teaching foreign languages. This thesis discusses the importance, place, advantages, and methodological role of distance education in teaching English.

Keywords: English, distance studying, methods, technology, language, translate, ICT.

INTRODUCTION

Scientific research in the field of distance learning for people of different ages and backgrounds is being conducted in almost all countries of the world. Previously, training was limited to studying numerous printed sources or listening to audio recordings with English dialogues and texts. In the modern period of development of methods of teaching foreign languages, distance learning is coming to the fore.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The main problem why distance learning methods began to develop is the rapid dissemination of information and the great distance between those who want to learn and those who want to teach from each other. The difficulty of self-education, even using the best materials, without regular contact with a teacher is obvious. Independent study of the English language practically does not bring results: a student can easily spoil his pronunciation in an attempt to remember words on his own, without the help of a teacher. Without systematic and effective feedback from the teacher, no courses or teaching materials will help you learn the language at the proper level.

That is why, in recent years, the world's leading educational institutions have started or are planning to start research in the field of distance learning in foreign languages, including such a popular language as English. Most of the methods presented on the Internet can be divided into two large groups: independent study of the English language using the materials provided and distance learning by communicating with a teacher through modern communication means: webinars or Skype, Zoom conferences [2].

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The overall effectiveness of teaching English remotely depends on several components [3]:

- use of the latest and classical pedagogical technologies;
- effectiveness and feedback opportunities;
- the effectiveness of the classes and the interaction between the student and the teacher;
- the effectiveness of the methods used and the professionalism of the teacher;
- personal motivation of the student.

Thus, the quality of the knowledge gained and the overall success of distance learning always depend on the methodological quality of the materials used and the method of organizing classes [1].

Technical solutions for distance learning

Currently available information technologies have at their disposal practically unlimited possibilities for processing, placement, storage and, which is very important for remote techniques, delivery of any data, of any volume and to any distance. In such conditions, the main issue remains the choice of a teacher and his organizational abilities. This means: the selection of material for learning, teaching methods and the general structure of the educational process. It is necessary to understand exactly what conceptual pedagogical methods underlie the construction of a distance learning course in English. Most often, all methods share the following characteristics:

1. Training in which the main burden falls on the student. Independent work is focused on developing the necessary language skills and mastering different types of written and oral speech. Such distance learning requires good didactic material, presented in a convenient and understandable form. This is a fairly flexible method of distance learning - knowledge can be acquired when and where it is convenient for the student. He can read or listen to materials on the road or at home, during his lunch break or in a cafe.

2. The student must have some mandatory skills: he must be able to use a personal computer, popular programs for communication and learning (Zoom, Skype, Tell Me More system and others). The student must be proficient in different types of independent work: be able to work with electronic dictionaries and reference books, be able to search, study and introductory reading. Of course, with a well-designed English language course, all necessary materials are provided immediately, and questions and difficulties in learning are resolved during consultations and feedback seminars.

3. Distance learning should not be passive. Very often, during classes, even in small groups of 2-4 people, students behave passively. The teaching methodology involves the active involvement of students in cognitive activities, which involve acquiring knowledge and solving numerous linguistic communicative problems. Thus, learning via Zoom allows you to carry out various creative and scientific projects with the help of international organizations and direct native English speakers.

4. The issue of monitoring the assimilation of acquired knowledge and the ability to apply it in various life situations is very important. Such reviews should be systematic and based on clear and regular feedback. There should be separate consultations where complex issues will be considered and the teacher will be able to adequately assess what exactly is more difficult for the student. It is also worth using delayed control in the form of testing [5].

An effective distance learning model

Any distance learning methodology must always flexibly combine the systematic and operational interaction of a professional teacher and the independent cognitive work of the student. He can study both from recommended literature and from independently found information on the Internet. It is considered an excellent way to test language skills by watching feature films and scientific programs in English, perhaps with subtitles turned off at first.

If classes are not held individually, but in small groups, it is necessary to ensure the interaction of group members within the framework of joint language projects, possibly with the participation of foreigners who are native speakers. They usually organize discussions, presentations, and video seminars on certain topics. Even participation in international post-crossing - exchanging postcards with unfamiliar foreigners through the international Postcrossing program - will have a positive impact.

Progress monitoring should be carried out systematically and should be taken into account when the teacher draws up new lesson plans. Control can be carried out in the form of open and closed testing, real-time listening, writing reports and abstracts on various topics. To store results and report, it is recommended to use progressive programs of the Tell Me More training system or available services from Google. For online classes you will need a special web account, which is provided by various Internet services.

Electronic reference books, seminars and textbooks, divided into various modules, are used as didactic material. Each module should be aimed at studying one area of the language, but all modules should also have joint application in practice.

CONCLUSION

Modern methods of distance learning in English and other foreign languages should always include the “three pillars” of learning – obtaining information, independent work and monitoring the mastery of the material. The teacher should concentrate his work on the principles of: open interaction with the student and adjustment of educational modules, depending on the student’s success and goals. For

distance learning, all the achievements of computer technology and software are used: audio books, online webinars and personal communication via Zoom and other online video chats. Language portals and the latest technologies offer the widest opportunities for students: you can study in small groups or individually, without leaving your home, receiving all the necessary materials to your email address or to your personal account.

REFERENCES

1. Abduzokhurovna, S. M., Qizi, K. K. A., & Khatamovna, K. G. (2019). Pragmatic and functional features of English aphorisms. *Достижения науки и образования*, (13 (54)), 33-34.
2. Andreev A.A. Introduction to distance learning. – M.: VU, 2017. – 276 p.
3. Averkieva L.G., Chaika Yu.A. ISSN 1997-2911 Philology. Issues of theory and practice, No. 1 (8) 2021.
4. Hatamovna, K. G., & Qizi, K. K. A. (2022). THE EFFECTIVENESS OF LINGUOCULTURAL APPROACH TO DEVELOP SOCIOLINGUISTIC COMPETENCE OF ESP STUDENTS. *Достижения науки и образования*, (3 (83)), 27-29.
5. Umarova, F., Xaydarova, G., & Raimjanova, M. (2024). Potential of Ecotourism in Uzbekistan: Regional Aspect. In *E3S Web of Conferences* (Vol. 574, p. 06006). EDP Sciences.
6. Ostonov, O., Khalikova, S., Raimjanova, U., & Umarova, F. (2023). The Role of Historical Knowledge in the Development of Uzbek Tourism. *SGS-Engineering & Sciences*, 2(02).
7. Jurayeva, M., Umarova, F., & Kholmurodova, E. (2024). THE EFFECTIVENESS OF GENDER APPROACHES IN HIGHER EDUCATION SYSTEM. *Science and innovation*, 3(Special Issue 15), 707-710.

8. Sheranov, Q., Umarova, F., & Sharapova, D. (2025). EFFECTS OF BEHAVIOURAL THERAPY FOR SCHIZOPHRENIA AND BIPOLAR AFFECTIVE DISORDER. *Modern Science and Research*, 4(1), 307-315.
9. Karamysheva T. V. Learning foreign languages with the help of a computer: in questions and answers. - St. Petersburg: "Soyuz", 2021.
10. Kenjaeva, K., Baxitjanova, E., & Khojanova, G. (2024). Directions of Ecotourism Organization in Uzbekistan. In *E3S Web of Conferences* (Vol. 574, p. 06005). EDP Sciences.
11. Kozimovna, T. Z. (2023). TILSHUNOSLIKDA DISKURS TUSHUNCHASI MOHIYATINING YORITILSHI. *Central Asian Research Journal for Interdisciplinary Studies (CARJIS)*, (4 (16)), 34-39.
12. Kulkarni, S., Singh, D., Hussain, L., Balaji, V., Sharma, A., Jumaniyozov, K., & Kenjaeva, K. (2024). Finite element analysis of bonded, riveted and hybrid joints in glass fibre epoxy composite laminates for aircraft structure. In *E3S Web of Conferences* (Vol. 563, p. 02006). EDP Sciences.
13. Polat E.S. Organization of distance learning in a foreign language based on computer telecommunications [Electronic resource] / E.S. Polat, Dr. Ped. Sciences, prof., head. laboratory DO. // Journal Open Education. – 2018. – Access mode: www.e-joe.ru/sod/98/1_98/st007.html (date of access: 03/03/2014).
14. Potapova R.K. New information technologies and linguistics: textbook. allowance - M.: KomKniga, 2015.
15. Software package for distance learning of foreign languages TMM [Electronic resource] // Professional solutions "Liter". – 2014. – Access mode: http://leater.com/RU/system_integration/complex_solutions/education/tmm/ (date of access: 03/03/2014).
16. Sysoev P.V., Evstigneev M.N. Modern Internet resources for teaching a foreign language // Foreign languages at school. 2018. No. 6. P. 2–9.

17. Tuxtayevich, K. I. ., Ahmatovna, P. S. ., Turgunbayevna, M. N., Rasulovna, R. M. ., Qizi, T. F. R. ., & Qizi, Y. N. A. . (2024). Different Approaches to Enhance Critical Thinking in Digital Education. *SPAST Reports*, 1(7). <https://spast.org/ojspath/article/view/5086>
18. Vladimirova L.P. Internet in foreign language classes. *IYASH*, No. 3, 2022. P. 33-41.
19. Zimnyaya I.A. Psychology of teaching foreign languages at school. - M.: Education, 2011.